

A Low-Cost Bench for Training Students in Power Amplifier and Digital Predistortion

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Abstract—This paper presents a low-cost bench to provide a comprehensive set of measurement capabilities to train students in RF Integrated Circuits characterization and their enhancement with a focus on Power Amplifier (PA) and its associated Digital Predistortion (DPD). It brings into play two Universal Software Radio Peripherals (USRP) and a user-friendly interface to perform measurements on a radio-frequency (RF) chain and to extract circuit characteristics. The interface was designed on MATLAB App Designer to provide students with an ergonomic and pedagogical user experience. Additionally, DPD software was designed for students to evaluate various PA linearization models and benchmark their performances. Furthermore, students can use this bench to test and validate their own circuit designs, providing hands-on experience and helping them to gain a better understanding of the principles of RF design. Finally, a survey displays feedback on students’ pedagogical appreciation of the bench.

Index Terms—Measurement Bench, Radiofrequency (RF), USRP, Digital Predistortion (DPD), Power Amplifier (PA).

I. INTRODUCTION

DIGITAL communications techniques (OFDM, carrier aggregation) increase considerably the spectral efficiency of communications to meet their exponential growth. However, these techniques generate signals with high Peak-to-Average-Power Ratio (PAPR). They are very sensitive to the non-linearities and memory effects introduced by the Power Amplifier (PA) [1], [2]. These effects distort the amplitude and phase of the useful signal, leading to asymmetric spectral regrowth in adjacent communication channels [3]–[5] and degradation of the Error Vector Magnitude (EVM).

Therefore, in order to be compliant with the linearity specifications of the latest communication standards [6] the use of linearization techniques has become necessary. They allow the PA to operate near their saturation point which improves the linearity versus power added efficiency (PAE) trade-off [7], [8]. Digital Predistortion (DPD) techniques have been investigated in the past decades as powerful linearization solutions. These methods aim to compensate amplitude, phase, and memory effects non-linearities with a predistorter (PD).

The ability to reduce power consumption, improve linearity and reduce system complexity have made digital DPD techniques increasingly used in the industry. PA with integrated DPD are available from multiple manufacturers [9]–[11]. Although all of the above concepts are studied and simulated in most Master’s level electronics courses, the practical aspects can be more restricted as the RF measurement instruments for studying these systems may be expensive as

Fig. 1: Cost of RF measurement instruments covering a frequency range up to at least 6GHz

shown in Fig. 1. Such instruments also often require a high level of expertise to operate, making them difficult and time-consuming to use. Consequently, many educational institutions are turning to USRP-based measurement benches [12], [13] as a cost-effective and user-friendly alternative to traditional RF measurement instruments.

In this paper, we present a low-cost ($\approx 2500\$$) USRP-based measurement bench for DPD training. RF signals are generated with USRPs and the DPD is performed in MATLAB. An interface monitors and configures the bench using the MATLAB App Designer feature. The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the measurement bench. Section III introduces the control interface of the bench with practical measurement examples. In Section IV, the students’ experiences and feedback from using the bench are discussed. Finally, conclusions and future work are stated in Section V.

II. THE MEASUREMENT BENCH

The measurement bench consists of two software radios and a computer running MATLAB. The two software radios are connected to the computer via a USB port. The USRP B200 generates the RF signal (TX waveform), which can be either a modulation or an arbitrary waveform. The USRP B200 is a single-channel, half-duplex transceiver featuring a frequency range of 70MHz - 6GHz, a sample rate of up to 56MHz, a spurious-free dynamic range of over 80 dB, and a maximum transmit power of up to 15dBm. The USRP B210 is used to sample the generated signal (RX waveform) after its propagation through an RF chain. The USRP B210 has the same parameters as the USRP B200 but can receive two channels simultaneously. MATLAB is used to create the TX waveform and analyze the RX waveform collected by the USRP B210. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. There are three possible configurations for this measuring bench :

- **Configuration 1:** the USRP B200 sends a signal to the device under test (DUT) and is received by the USRP B210.
- **Configuration 2:** the USRP B200 sends a signal, half of which is transmitted to the DUT, and the other half is directly received by the first port of the USRP B210. The output signal from the DUT is received by the second RX port of the USRP B210. This configuration provides a more accurate estimation of the DUT's characteristics since it does not require any synchronization between the devices, and the input/output of the DUT is directly sampled.
- **Configuration 3:** only one USRP is used for both transmitting and receiving. However, since these devices

TABLE I: MEASUREMENT CAPABILITIES OF EACH CONFIGURATION

Configuration	1	2	3
Gain/Loss	✓✓	✓✓	✓
Phase	✓✓	✓✓	✓
Intermodulation products (IMD)	✓✓	✓✓	✓
Bit Error Rate (BER)	✓	✓✓	×
Error Vector Magnitude (EVM)	✓	✓✓	×
Digital Predistorsion (DPD)	✓	✓✓	×

are not designed for full-duplex purposes, only half of the available bandwidth can be used for measurements, and synchronizing the TX and RX modes can be challenging.

Fig. 3 presents the schematic for each configuration. Table I presents the measurement capabilities for each configuration. A double check mark (✓✓) stands for "accurate measurement", one check mark (✓) stands for "feasible measurement but the synchronization makes it difficult" and a cross (×) stands for "not available".

The gain, loss, phase shift, and intermodulation products of a device can be evaluated in all configurations over a wide frequency range (70MHz-6GHz). Measurements on modulated signals (BER, EVM) and DPD applications are possible only in configurations 1 and 2 as full-duplex communications are challenging in configuration 3. These configurations provide the user with measurement options that can be used for a set of experiments and applications at a low cost ($\approx 2500\$$).

Fig. 2: Photograph of the measurement bench in configuration 1

Fig. 3: Configurations

III. THE CONTROL INTERFACE

The bench's control interface was created using the MATLAB App Designer feature [14]. Communications, signal processing, and USRP-related toolboxes [15]–[17] are required to use the interface. Two examples are provided to help understand how the software works. The first example focuses on generating a modulated signal, which is transmitted at a specific RF frequency. The protocol for this example is described as follows.

Step 1: When launching the application, the user needs to decide the configuration chosen (1, 2 or 3). For the first example, configuration 1 is chosen. The first step is to configure the USRP that will be used. The USRP configuration window is displayed in Fig. 4. The different configuration parameters are listed below:

- TX/RX: The USRP model (B200 or B210 for the moment)
- TX/RX: The serial number of the device
- TX/RX: The carrier frequency f_{RF} (from 70MHz to 6GHz), a local oscillator offset can also be specified
- TX/RX: The master clock rate of the USRP M_{CLK} (maximum value = 61.44MHz)
- TX/RX: The gain of the intern USRP PA, which is directly related to the maximum output power delivered by the device
- TX/RX: The interpolation/decimation factor I/D (The MATLAB sample rate F_s is equal to M_{clk}/I for the transmitter and M_{clk}/D for the receiver)

Fig. 4: The USRP(s) configuration panel

- TX/RX: The data type conversion from MATLAB (int8 or int16)
- TX/RX: the use of internal, external or GPSDO sources for the clock/PPS
- TX/RX: The use of a "Burst Mode" to avoid underruns/overruns during the transmission
- RX: The number of samples per frame at the reception
- RX: The output data type of the signal at the reception
- RX: The number of frames that will be received

A USRP configuration setup can be stored or loaded (from the current workspace folder or from the file explorer) to avoid entering all the parameters each time the measurement bench is used. The parameters chosen for the example are displayed on the control interface in Fig. 4.

Step 2: Once the USRP is configured and connected, you can choose the waveform that will be transmitted. Three waveforms are available for the moment:

- One tone
 - Parameters: frequency, number of samples, average power
 - Measurements: Gain, Phase
- Two tones
 - Parameters: frequency 1, frequency 2, number of samples, average power
 - Measurements: Gain, Phase, IMD
- An M-QAM OFDM modulation
 - QAM Parameters: Modulation order, bandwidth, number of symbols, bit rate, symbol rate, average power
 - OFDM Parameters: For the moment these parameters are fixed to 64 sub-carriers without pilots
 - Measurements: Gain, Phase, IMD, DPD (ACPR), EVM, BER

The sample rate F_s of the signal is defined during the configuration of the USRP. A feature to plot the transient waveform, power spectrum, IQ constellation, or power histogram of the generated waveform is also available. As for the USRP configuration, a generated waveform can be

Fig. 5: The waveform generator panel

stored or loaded. The parameters of the chosen waveform for the example are displayed on the control interface in Fig. 5.

Step 3a: Once the USRP(s) are configured and the waveform is generated, different options to transmit the signal are available.

- **Duration mode:** transmit during a preselected duration
- **Duration with intervals:** transmit during a preselected duration with small intervals without transmission
- **Continuous mode:** transmit until the user decides to stop the communication
- **Continuous mode with intervals:** Same as continuous but with intervals without transmission

The transmission can be canceled by the user at any moment. Furthermore, in configurations 1 and 2, synchronization of the TX and RX USRP(s) can be achieved using a UDP protocol. The TX unit signals the RX unit to enter reception mode when a transmission starts. Upon reception of the predetermined number of frames, the RX unit notifies the TX unit to stop the transmission.

After receiving a signal, the user can analyze it using various visualization tools, such as transient, power spectrum, and power histogram, or export it as a datafile for further examination in a workspace outside the application.

In the context of the first application example, the spectrum of the transmitted signal obtained in configuration 1 is compared to the spectrum obtained with a traditional measuring device, the N9324C Spectrum Analyzer from Keysight, to showcase the advantages of this bench. Fig. 6 indicates that the USRP spectrum analyzer can achieve similar measurement resolution as the Keysight device. Furthermore, as the measured signal is in the baseband, it can be demodulated to evaluate the BER and EVM.

The second example to showcase the use of the bench is to perform a DPD on a self-made power amplifier. Since the

Fig. 6: Spectra of a modulated signal measured with a spectrum analyzer N9324C and an USRP B210 (superposed)

Fig. 7: The DPD measurement panel

signal used is the same as in the first example, steps 1 and 2 are the same.

Step 3b: Once the USRP(s) are configured and the waveform is generated, the measurement tab is available to perform DPD measurements or device characterization. In this example, the DPD tab is chosen. The DPD configuration panel is displayed in Fig. 7. The parameters for the DPD configuration are: the mathematical model used of the predistorter (Memory polynomial (MP) or generalized memory polynomial (GMP)), the algorithm used to process the predistorter, the data length for the process and the number of times the process is iterated to converge to a better predistorter model. On the right side of the panel, different information regarding the current DPD iteration is displayed. Once the DPD is finished, the user can plot power spectra, transient, and constellation graphs. On these graphs, ACPR and EVM measurements can be evaluated. The data can also be exported in a .mat for complementary studies.

To illustrate this measurement tool, a DPD was applied on a

Fig. 8: Spectra of PA output signal with and without DPD

9dB Gain 2.5GHz self-made PA. Spectra of the output signal of the PA without and with DPD are displayed in Fig. 8. Without DPD, the output power of the main channel was 7dBm (input power is -2dBm) and the power in adjacent channels was -27.46dBm (left channel) and -27.75dBm (right channel). With the DPD, the same output power was kept but the power in adjacent channels was reduced to -35.71dBm (left channel) and -35.68dBm (right channel). Therefore, the ACPR went from -34.46/-34.75dBc to -42.71/-42.68dBc.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND FEEDBACK FROM STUDENTS

This section showcases the outcomes of an experiment conducted by students on a DPD measurement bench, along with a survey that solicited feedback on its usage. The purpose was to validate its efficiency for future DPD and RF measurement courses. Following [18], 16 students enrolled in postgraduate studies at the Univ. Bordeaux evaluated several statements by rating them from 1 to 5. The results displayed in Table II indicate that the students found the bench to be a valuable, pedagogical, and practical resource for DPD and RF measurement courses, as demonstrated by the high average scores for the different statements. Additionally, students were asked to provide written comments on each statement, and a selection of these comments is presented below.

- **About the demonstration:** “You don’t need all the theory of the DPD to understand how the bench works and why it is important”, “Good review course on PA digital predistortion”.
- **About the DPD understanding:** “Live visualization of the spectra with and without DPD gives us a directly visible impact of the process”, “Better than a course: a demonstration and presentation with animations”.
- **About the control interface:** “Well-designed tabs to simplify the use of the bench”, “The interface is clean and intuitive”.
- **About ease of use compared to RF measurement tools:** “No need for device calibration”, “Easier to use because

TABLE II: NUMERICAL SURVEY (AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION) OF A GROUP OF STUDENTS

Question	Group Average	Standard Deviation
The demonstration of the bench helped me to understand what DPD is	4.8	0.44
This bench helped me to understand the DPD (more than theoretical courses)	4.8	0.63
The interface driving the measurement bench is ergonomic and easy to use	4.6	0.60
The measurement bench is easier to use than conventional tools	4.9	0.63
This measurement bench has motivated me to further investigations	3.9	0.93
I recommend the use of this bench for other courses	4.9	0.54

all is centralized”, “Everything is centralised and easily exportable”.

- **On the appeal of digital communications/RF and DPD measures:** “If there is not too much code to program I am interested”.
- **About the use of this bench for other courses:** “A useful bench for understanding the frequency spectrum of modulated signals”, “Easier to use than MATLAB simulations for digital communications”, “Easy to handle to understand what’s going on in the circuit”.

The majority of the suggestions for enhancing this bench revolved around the concept of incorporating modulation schemes, measurement templates and make a user manual with demos. These recommendations will be taken into account for future developments of the bench. Furthermore, this bench will be displayed under an open-source format as an editable script and an executable file to give access to other educators to user-friendly and cost-effective tools for conducting practical digital communications, RF, and DPD measurements.

V. CONCLUSION

A pedagogical low-cost measurement bench for training in PA DPD was presented in this paper. The measurement bench, costing less than 2500\$, offers a range of functionalities including Gain/Phase IMD, BER, EVM, and ACPR measurements. The bench is conveniently controlled via an open-access MATLAB interface, which enables easy and efficient DPD measurements, as well as DUT characterization on RF devices. Furthermore, the survey presented in this paper shows students’ acceptance of the utilization of this bench in future DPD, RF measurements, and digital communications courses. This low-cost measurement bench presents a valuable tool not only for educational purposes but also for practical applications in the field of PA DPD.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Nicolas Marin who designed the very first version of the control interface. The project HERMES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 964246.

Publication reflects only the author's view, the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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